

METHODOLOGY FOR IMPROVING THE OFFENSIVE TECHNIQUE OF QUALIFIED HANDBALL PLAYERS BASED ON KINEMATIC PARAMETERS

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Annotation: This article analyzes the importance of improving the technical preparedness of handball players and its impact on sports results. Effective technical preparation plays a crucial role in enhancing performance and team outcomes, aiding in making correct decisions and applying technical methods in various game situations. Mastering technique and continuously developing it is considered essential for achieving high sporting results.

Keywords: handball, technical preparedness, performance, team outcomes, technique mastery, sports results, game situations.

Team handball is an important Olympic sport that is played professionally in international competitions. In team handball matches, successfully attacking and scoring against the opponent's goal is a crucial factor in achieving victory [2]. To maximize the number of goals scored during a match, handball players—particularly backcourt players who shoot from positions more than 8 meters away from the goal—are required to optimize the accuracy and speed of their throws. Depending on their position in the game and the movements of the defending opponents, team handball players utilize various types of throwing techniques [3]. All actions in handball are performed under specific conditions—that is, in the presence of opposing team players and in accordance with the rules of the game. Therefore, the selection and execution of movements largely depend on the situations that arise during the match. Although, in some cases, a player may perform certain technical actions in an unconventional manner, most technical elements are associated with specific kinematic parameters that reflect the efficiency of their execution [4]. In improving the offensive technical actions of handball players, it is essential to take into account their kinematic parameters. In particular, the maximum angular values of body segments during jump shots play a significant role in organizing the technical training process.

The technical preparedness of each athlete is assessed based on the range of technical skills they have thoroughly mastered and can apply effectively in game situations. The athletic preparation of handball players is directly linked to the gradual development of their technical proficiency. Therefore, one of the

primary objectives of training sessions is to comprehensively and deeply acquire handball techniques. To effectively achieve this goal, the following requirements must be met:

1. To master all modern elements of game technique equally and to be able to perform them using more advanced methods under various game conditions;
2. To master the most frequently used offensive and defensive techniques in the context of team movements;
3. To continuously improve the coherence of technical techniques used in free and initiative movements, and to regularly enhance the quality of their execution.

The process of improving a handball player's technical preparedness is carried out based on general theoretical principles and is closely linked to the development of tactical thinking, the formation of movement qualities, and the strengthening of volitional and moral qualities. During training, it is important to identify ways to perform technical techniques more effectively. For this, it is necessary to develop the athlete's movement qualities, such as agility, speed, strength, endurance, and flexibility, to a high level [6].

The overall performance level of the team is directly determined by the technical preparedness of the players. During technical preparation, all necessary technical methods are gradually mastered, which leads to the improvement of both the athlete's individual abilities and the development of team movements.

Various pedagogical methods are used in improving technique, with the most widely used being the method of repetition. Additionally, different competition methods are also considered an effective tool in reinforcing technical skills.

Technique is the foundation of handball, and mastering it perfectly and being able to apply it correctly in various game situations is a crucial factor in achieving high sporting results.

CONCLUSION

The technical preparedness of handball players is one of the key factors in shaping their athletic skill. It plays an important role in executing effective actions during the game, making correct decisions in harmony with tactics, and improving team performance. Mastering technique and being able to apply it in various game situations is a guarantee of achieving high sporting results. During the training process, the correct selection of repetition, competition, and other

pedagogical methods, as well as the continuous development of the athlete's physical qualities, are crucial in improving technical proficiency. Therefore, the continuous enhancement of technical preparedness is an essential condition for improving sports results and training highly skilled handball players.

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